

Project Report On
METAL DETECTOR

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KRISHNADEVARAYA GOVT. POLYTECHNIC
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Project Report on

Metal Detector

Under the Guidance of

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This is to certify that the project entitled

'METAL DETECTOR'

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Yours Sincerely,

The Students of the Project

Metal Detector

Electronics & Instrumentation Engg.
during the Academic Year 2004-2005.

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ABSTRACT

The main aim of the project is to detect the metal near by to the sensor.

Whenever the metal is brought near the sensor (inductor) a buzzer is produced from the speaker and whenever the metal is removed the sound is switched Off.

As the magnetic Flux passes through the some opaque objects such as Plastics, Cloth, etc., by which we can detect any metal hiding behind some objects.

GENERALIZED MEASUREMENT SYSTEM

The term "Instrumentation system" includes the sensing element, variable conversion and manipulation elements, data transmission and data presentation these are realized with suitable transducer, signal conditioners and recording equipment.

SYSTEM CONFIGURATION :

A generalized instrumentation system compress the following elements they are

- a) The transducer which converts the measured (Measured quantity property or condition) in to a suitable electrical output.
- b) The signal conditioner, which converts the transducer, output in to an electrical quantity suitable for control recording and / or display.
- c) The display or readout devices which display the required information about the measured generally in engineering units.
- d) The electrical power supply, which provides the required excitation to the transducer and the necessary electrical power to the signal conditioners and display.

TRANSDUCER :

A transducer is defined as a device which, when activated by one form of energy, is capable of converting it to another form of energy. The transudation may be from mechanical, Electrical or optical to any other related from. The transducer provides a usable output in response to a specific input measured, which may be in physical or mechanical quantity, property or condition.

In transducers there are two types :

- 1) Mechanical Transducer
- 2) Electrical Transducer

In instrumentation system, Electrical transducer are used due to poor frequency response, requirement of large forces and to over come mechanical friction that are caused by mechanical transducers.

An electrical transducer is a sensing device by which a physical or Mechanical or optical quantity to be measured is transformed directly with a suitable mechanism in to an electrical voltage or current proportional to the input measured. The output to input and the output to time behaviour is predictable to know degree of accuracy, sensitivity and response, with in the specified environmental conditions. The significant parameters, which dictate the transducer capability, are linearity, repeatability, resolutions and reliability.

Since the output can be modified, modulated or amplified at will, the output signal can be easily adapted from recording on any suitable multi channel recording oscillograph. Even the shape and size of transducer can be suitably designed to achieve the optimum weight and volume. The control design and dimension can be so chosen not to disturb the measured phenomenon.

The electrical transducers are classified under two category viz., active and passive transducers.

Active transducers are self generating devices, operating under energy conversion principles. These generate an equivalent electrical output signal.

Eg. From pressure to charge (or)

From temperature to electric, potential

Examples of active transducers are: Thermoelectric, photovoltaic, Piezoelectric, Electromagnetic, Galvanic etc., passive transducers operate under energy controlling principles. They depend upon the change in the electrical parameter (Resistance, inductance or capacitance) whose excitation or operation requires secondary electrical source from an external source.

A typical example is in the case of strain guage excited by a D.C. voltage source or differential transformer energized as a carrier wave signal.

Examples of passive transducer are Resistive, inductive, capacitive, half effect, photo conductive etc.

BASIC REQUIREMENTS OF A TRANSDUCER :

A transducer is normally designed to sense a specific measured or to respond only to the particular measured. A complete knowledge of the electrical and mechanical characteristics of the transducer is of great importance while choosing a transducer for a particular application during the selection of instrumentation for the experiment concerned, the following requirements should be possessed by the transducer. They are

- a) Ruggedness
- b) Linearity
- c) Repeatability
- d) Convenient instrumentation
- e) High Stability and Reliability
- f) Good Dynamic Response
- g) Excellent mechanical characteristics that can effect the performance in static, quasistatic and dynamic states.

SIGNAL CONDITIONER :

The Signal conditioner can vary in complexity from a simple resistance network or impedance matching network to complex multistage amplifiers with or without detectors, demodulators and filters alternately, they are termed as signal modifiers or signal processors. The output signal may be an analog or digital quantity.

The signal conditioning stage of vibration transducers depend upon the type of transduction employed. Starting with the connecting cable, the associated signal amplifier, integrating or differentiation circuits, filters, modulators and demodulators with the balancing arrangements, if any perform important functions in signal conditioning system employing a piezo electric transducer compress the cable connecting the transducer to the amplifier signal amplifier, signal modifier if any and output display or recorder.

DISPLAYS :-

The Readout of display devices may be in analog or digital format. The simplest form of a display device is the common panel meter with some kind of calibrated scale or pointer. In digital displays numeric print outs are obtained whenever a permanent record is necessary. The analog signal it self can be recorded permanently on a self balancing type potentiometric strip chart recorder (or) an ultra violet galvanometer type oscillography.

Graphic pen type galvanometer recorders are also employed in case where the signal frequency is 1010. If the signal is digital, the information can be printed out and stored on a paper with a Tele printer line printer or mosaic printer or recorded in a paper tape, punch card, Magnetic tape, (Cassette) or floppy disc. The main advantage of these devices high accuracy high speed and elimination of human operation errors.

METAL DETECTOR

CONSTRUCTION :

The circuit consist of three Transistors, Resistors, Capacitors, Diodes, Air Core Inductor, loud speakers, I.C. and 9v D.C. supply for the working of transistor and supply for I.C. as well as speaker (if required).

The circuit also consist of a ceramic filter (Equalizer).

WORKING :

It is a very simple circuit to understand. It works on the principle of super Hetrodyne. It consist of two oscillators one is colpitts oscillator and other has a ceramic filter which is commonly used in the intermediate frequency sound section in T.V. and both the frequencies combine to mixer [transistor (T_2)] and from the Transistor T_2 of the collector is taken out and given the two diodes known as detector stage and then to the filter and then to IC (TDA 2822) which is a stereo Amplifier which amplifies to the loud speaker.

Actually the first oscillator is fixed at 5.5 MHz and other oscillator known as colpitts is selected to 5.5 MHz frequency by using a available capacitor called trimmer. Then the capacitance is changed by varying the capacitance of the capacitor before varying see that no metal is in contact with the inductor. After changing the capacitance the two frequencies are equal hence there is no sound. When any metal is bought under the contact of the frequency (colpitts oscillator) changes hence the difference of the frequency is taken and hence there is an output. This output is amplified and given to the speaker.

CIRCUIT DIAGRAM OF METAL DETECTOR

RESISTOR

RESISTOR :

Resistor is defined as the opposition to the flow of current.

RESISTANCE :

It is the property of a resistor which opposes the flow of electrons through it.

Fixed Resistor

CHARACTERISTICS :

Two types of characteristics

1. It is measured in * (Ohms) and is indicated by letter R.
2. Power ratings 0.1 watts to several hundred watts.

Basically it is classified in to three types.

- a) Low resistance $0 < R < 10$ ohm's
- b) Medium resistance $1 < R < 100K$
- c) High resistance $100 < R < \text{infinity}$

TYPES OF RESISTORS :

Resistors :

1. Fixed resistors.
2. Variable resistors

Fixed Resistors :

- a) Carbon Resistor
- b) Cracked Carbon Resistor
- c) Wire wound Resistor
- d) Metal film Resistor
- e) Metal Oxide Resistor
- f) Moulded Resistor
- g) Insulated mould Resistor

Variable Resistor :

- a) Wire wound resistor
- b) Carbon potentiometer
- c) Trimmer
- d) Polyester film Resistor
 - 1) Symmetrical
 - 2) Non Symmetrical
- e) NTC Thermistor
- f) PTC Thermistor

COLOUR CODING :

The resistance values are coded on the resistors using various codes like EIA code, BS 1825 and dot code normally the resistor values may be indicated by four colour code bands.

The first colour band, second colour band, indicates the first two digits of resistor value. Third colour band indicates the multiplying factor the fourth colour band indicates the tolerance value.

In the colour code, the colour bands are as follows :

Black	-	0
Brown	-	1
Red	-	2
Orange	-	3
Yellow	-	4
Green	-	5
Blue	-	6
Violet	-	7
Grey	-	8
White	-	9

Tolerance in the colour codes given as follows :

Gold	-	$\pm 5\%$
Silver	-	$\pm 10\%$
Unknown Colour	-	$\pm 20\%$

DIODE

DIODE DEFINITION :

It is a semiconductor device which allows the flow of current in one direction and opposes in the other direction.

SEMI CONDUCTOR DIODE :

A semiconductor diode allows current to flow easily in one direction but not in the other i.e., its resistance is low in conducting direction but very high in the opposite direction. A diode has two terminals, the anode and the cathode.

There are several kinds of diodes, those are :

- a) Junction Diode
- b) P-I-N Diode
- c) Varactor Diode
- d) Zener Diode
- e) Tunnel Diode
- f) Selenium Diode, etc.,

SCHEMATIC SYMBOLS OF VARIOUS DIODES :

PN JUNCTION DIODE & ITS SYMBOL :

(a) P-N Junction Diode and its Symbol

V-I CHARACTERISTICS OF PN JUNCTION DIODE :

Fig 1

Volt ampere (V-I) Characteristics of PN junction diode is the curve between voltage across the junction and the circuit current usually, voltage

is taken along x-axis and current along y-axis. The characteristics can be studied under three sections namely Zero external voltage, forward bias & reverse bias.

ZERO EXTERNAL VOLTAGE :

When the external voltage is zero i.e., the circuit is open the current conduction is not permitted by the barrier, therefore the circuit current is zero as indicated by "0" in above figure.

FORWARD BIAS :

Under forward bias condition potential barrier of a PN junction is reduced. At some forward voltage, the potential barrier is eliminated and current starts flowing in the circuit. Further the magnitude of current increases with the increase in a applied forward voltage thus, a rising curve OB is obtained with forward bias as shown in the figure. From the forward characteristic, it is seen that at first (region OA), the current increase very slowly and the curve is non linear. The PN junction behaves like an ordinary

conductor therefore, the current rises very sharply with increase in external voltage and the curve is almost linear.

REVERSE BIAS :

Under reverse bias condition the potential barrier of a PN junction diode is increased. Therefore the junction resistance become very high and practically no current flows through the circuit.

However, in practice, a very small current flows in circuit with reverse bias as shown in the reverse characteristic. This is called reverse current and is due to the minority carriers. If reverse voltage is increased continuously, the kinetic energy of minority carriers becomes high enough to knock out electrons from the semiconductor atoms. At this stage break down of the junction occurs characterized by a sudden rise of reverse current fall of the resistance of barrier region.

DIODE APPLICATIONS :

1. **PN Diode :** Rectifier, Switch, Clipper, Clamper, Demodulator
2. **Zener Diode :** Voltage regulator
3. **Tunnel Diode :** High speed switching, amplifier, oscillator
4. **Photo Diode :** Counter, light intensity measuring device.
5. **Varactor Diode :** Oscillator, automatic frequency controller
6. **Light Emitting Diode :** Indicator lamps, displays.

DIODE SPECIFICATIONS :**Maximum Forward Current (I_F) :-**

It is the maximum current in forward bias that a P-N junction can conduct with damage to the junction.

Peak inverse voltage (PIV) :

It is the maximum voltage that can be applied in reverse bias. The P-N junction without damage to the junction.

Reverse Break Down Voltage (V_{BR}) :

The minimum reverse voltage at which the diode may break down.

Power Rating (P) :

The maximum power that the device can safely dissipate on a continuous basis in free air at 25°C.

Surge Current (I_{f_Surge}) :

It is usually higher than the normal maximum forward current. It may flow briefly when a circuit is first switched on.

TRANSISTOR

DEFINATION OF TRANSISTOR :

Transistor is three terminal semi conductor devices consist of emitter, base and collector.

Transistor has two junctions namely

- a) Emitter base junction. (It is always forward bias)
- b) Collector base junction. (It is always reverse bias)

CONSTRUCTION OF TRANSISTOR :

Transistor is equivalent to two diodes connected back to back. A transistor contains two N - type and one P - type of material it is known as NPN transistor or two P- type and one N-type layers material it is known as PNP transistor. The emitter layer is heavily doped, the base is lightly doped and the collector is only moderate doped. Base is thinner than the emitter, collector is wider than both base and emitter. The emitter base junction is always forward bias and collector base junction is always reverse bias. The resistance of emitter - base region is very small compared to collector base region.

Biasing of a Transistor for Active mode

CIRCUIT REPRESENTATION OF TRANSISTOR :

NPN

PNP

WORKING PRINCIPLE OF TRANSISTORS:

PNP Transistor :

Holes in P – type emitter flow in to the base. This constitutes the current I_E and only a few holes combine with the electrons in the base as it is highly doped and is also thin. The majority of the holes from the emitter cross over in to the collector region to constitute collector current I_C . Hence the conduction in a PNP transistor is by holes.

NPN TRANSISTOR :

Electrons in the N – type emitter flow into the base. This is the current I_E . These electrons flow into the P type base combine with the holes in the base, constituting current I_B . The majority of electrons cross over the collector region causing current I_C . Thus the total emitter current I_E is the sum of I_C and I_B i.e., $I_E = I_B + I_C$. Hence the current conduction in a NPN transistor is by electrons.

CONFIGURATION OF TRANSISTORS :

- 1) Common – base configuration
- 2) Common – emitter configuration
- 3) Common – collector configuration

COMMON – BASE CONFIGURATION :

In this arrangement input is applied between emitter and base. The base of the transistor is common to both input and output circuit and hence the name common base configuration.

COMMON – EMITTER CONFIGURATION :

In this arrangement input is applied between base and emitter and output is taken from the collector and emitter. The emitter of the transistor is common to both input and output circuit and hence the name common emitter configuration.

COMMON – COLLECTOR CONFIGURATION :

Input is applied between base and collector and output is taken from collector and emitter. The collector of the transistor is common to both input and output circuits and hence the name common collector configuration.

Principle :

Main principle of transistor is increases the strength of a weak signal and thus acts as an amplifier.

TRANSISTOR AS AN AMPLIFIER :

Transistor for an amplification can be connected in any one of three configurations. Here for simplicity CB connection is shown.

The signal is applied between emitter and base junction and output is taken across the load R_L connected in the collector circuit. The input circuit should be forward biased to achieve the amplification for this a DC voltage V_{EE} is applied in the input circuit in series with the signal. The DC voltage is known as bias voltage and magnitude should always be such that it keeps the input circuit forward biased.

The input circuit has low resistance, so a small change in signal voltage causes an appreciate change in emitter current. Due to transistor action this produces almost the same change in collector current. The collector current flowing through large load resistance R_L produces a large

voltage across it. In this way a weak signal applied in the input circuit appears in the amplified form in the collector circuit.

IMPORTANT POINTS ABOUT TRANSISTOR :

Transistor :

It is a three terminal semi conductor or device, namely emitter, base and collector. It has two junctions, i.e. emitter – base junction and collector – base junction.

Alpha :

It is common base current gain and it is denoted by a letter “ α ” and is defined as the ratio of collector current to emitter current. Its typical value is 0.98.

Beta :

The common emitter current gain is called as beta and it is denoted by letter “ β ” and its typical value varies from 50 to 200. It is the ratio of collector current to base current.

TRANSISTOR SPECIFICATIONS :

- a) Supply voltage (V_{cc})
- b) Current gain (α or β)
- c) Collector current (I_{Cmax})
- d) Collector to emitter voltage (V_{Cemax})
- e) Input impedance (R_i)
- f) Output impedance (R_o)
- g) Power dissipation (P) and
- h) Leakage Current (I_{Co})

TRANSISTOR APPLICATION :

- a) It is widely used as an amplifier.
- b) Transistor in common collector configuration is used as a buffer to match high impedance to low impedance.
- c) They are used in oscillators like colpitts, Hartley, wien bridge and phase shift oscillators.
- d) It is used as a switch.
- e) It is also used in clipping and clamping circuits
- f) Used in active filters
- g) Used in square wave generation circuits called multivibrators
- h) Used in digital circuits.

OSCILLATORS

INTRODUCTION :

Many electronic devices require a source of energy at specific frequency which may range from a few Hz to several MHz. This is achieved by an electronic device called an oscillator. Although it generates a frequency, it should be noted that it does not create energy.

Oscillators are extensively used in electronic equipment. For example in Radio and T.V. receivers, oscillators are used to generate high frequency wave (called carrier wave). Audio frequency and radio frequency signals are required for the repair of radio, T.V. and electronic equipment. Oscillators are also widely used in radar, computers and other electronic devices.

Oscillators can provide sinusoidal or non sinusoidal waves (Ex Square waves, triangular waves, saw tooth etc.,)

An amplifier has to satisfy the barkhausen criterion $[A\beta] = 1$ so as to work as an oscillator. Oscillator are classified in to various types like sinusoidal and non sinusoidal oscillators.

RC oscillators like RC phase shift and wein bridge incorporates RC network as frequency determining networks. LC oscillator like hartley, colpitts and tuned collector oscillators use in tank circuit as a frequency determine network. Crystal oscillators uses a quartz like crystal in the oscillators circuit. Crystal oscillator produces very stable frequency. The oscillator also used in signal generators, industrial applications, temperature controlled ovens and digital clocks etc.

CONDITIONS FOR AN AMPLIFIER TO WORK AS AN OSCILLATOR :

Oscillations produced by adequate positive feed back in an amplifier is called feed back oscillator. The figure shows the block diagram of feed back oscillator.

When the feed back signal is added to the input signal, then the magnitude of the input signal increases. Then it is known as positive feed back or regenerative feed back.

The gain of the circuit with feed back is

$$A_f = \frac{A}{(1 - AB)}$$

Where A = gain without feed back

β = Feed back factor

$A\beta$ = loop gain.

If $A\beta = 1$ then A_f becomes infinity hence the amplifier becomes unstable and works as an oscillator with zero input signal. The condition of the unity loop gain i.e. $A\beta = 1$ is called Barkhausen criterion.

Therefore an amplifier must satisfy the following conditions in order to work as an oscillator.

- 1) Positive feed back must be incorporated
- 2) $[A\beta] = 1$
- 3) The phase of $A\beta$ must be Zero degrees or integral multiples of 360° .

BLACK DIAGRAM OF OSCILLATOR :

HARTLEY OSCILLATOR :

Hartley oscillator

COLPITT'S OSCILLATOR :

Colpitt's oscillator is also an LC Oscillator used to generate RF signals. The circuit diagram of colpitt's oscillator is shown in figure.

Colpitt's Oscillator

The colpitt's oscillator consists of a transistor amplifier which operates in CE mode. The resistors R_1 , R_2 will provide self bias and R_E stabilizes the operating point. C_E is the bypass capacitor which increases the gain of the amplifier. R_E is the load resistor and the capacitor (C_C) is known as coupling or blocking capacitor.

WORKING :

The feedback network consists of a C_1 , C_2 and L . The feedback network determines the frequency of the oscillator. When the supply is "ON" a transient current is produced in the tank circuit and damped harmonic oscillations are setup in the circuit. The oscillator current in the tank circuit produces AC voltage across C_1 and C_2 . A part of Voltage appearing across C_1 is fed to the input. The feedback voltage is 180° out of phase shift with respect to output voltage. Since the transistor operates in CE

mode, it introduces 180° phase shift between its input and output voltages. Thus the total phase shift is 0° or 360° around the loop the feedback is adjusted. So that the loop gain $A\beta = 1$ then the circuit acts as an oscillator and produces a sinusoidal wave form of frequency F_0 determined by the LC circuit.

$$\text{Where } C = C_1 C_2 / (C_1 + C_2)$$

The condition for sustained oscillations is $h_{FE} = C_2 / C_1$.

APPLICATIONS OF OSCILLATIONS :

RC phase shift oscillators are used in

$$f_0 = \frac{1}{6.28\sqrt{RC}} \text{ Hz}$$

- 1) Audio frequency applications
- 2) Signal generators
- 3) Function generators

LC OSCILLATORS ARE USED IN :

- 1) Radio and TV receivers as load oscillator
- 2) For induction and dielectric heating purposes
- 3) For high frequency applications.

CRYSTAL OSCILLATORS ARE USED IN :

- 1) Radio and TV transmitters as carrier frequency generators.
- 2) In temperature controlled ovens.
- 3) Wrist Watches
- 4) Digital clocks
- 5) To maintain precision time standards.

MICRO - PHONE

MICRO - PHONES :

Micro - phones are transducers for converting sound energy into electrical energy. They serve two purposes they are used to convert speech signals into electrical signals and serve as measuring instruments converting sound signals into electrical current with accurate indicating meters.

TYPES OF MICRO - PHONES :

Different types of micro - phones are pressure micro phones, pressure gradient micro phones and combination of the two Micro Phones.

Micro phones are further classified as :

- 1) Carbon micro phone
- 2) Condenser micro phone
- 3) Moving coil micro phone
- 4) Electro - static micro phone
- 5) Piezo - electric micro phone.

CARBON MICRO PHONE :

CONDENSER MICRO PHONE :**CHARACTERISTICS OF MICRO PHONE :**

1. Frequency response
2. Sensitivity
3. Directional characteristics

FREQUENCY RESPONSE :

Frequency response of a microphone is the range of frequencies over which useful operation is obtained. The frequency response of different micro phone is as follows :

Moving coil micro phone	-	50 Hz to 10 KHz
Electrostatic Type	-	Below 1 KHz
Crystal Micro Phone	-	20 Hz to 10 KHz

SENSITIVITY :

Sensitivity is defined as response of micro phone to the impinging sound pressure.

A micro phone should have high sensitivity. This depends mainly on constructional features. The carbon micro phone and condenser micro phone are very sensitive micro phones.

DIRECTIONAL CHARACTERISTICS :

Directional characteristics gives us an indication of how the micro phones respond to sound impinging.

LOUD SPEAKERS :

A loud speaker is an Electro – magnetic transducer for converting electrical signals into sounds. There are two types in one the vibrating surface called diaphragm radiates sound directly into air and the second in which a horn is interposed between diaphragm and the air.

TYPES OF LOUD SPEAKERS :

1. Dynamic loud speaker (or) permanent magnet moving coil loud speaker (PMMC)
2. Electro Dynamic (or) Electro magnet moving coil loud speaker (EMMC)
3. Electrostatic loud speaker
4. Crystal loud speaker.

INDUCTOR

The relation between electricity and magnetism was discovered by Oersted in 1824, who found that moving current in a conductor can produce magnetic field, in other words, electrons in motion has an associated magnetic field. In converse to this phenomenon Faraday stated that moving magnetic field produces an electric field. These electromagnetic effect found in many electronic components such as "Inductors" and "Transformers"

An "inductor" or "Choke" is a coil of wire with a core of either air or a magnetic material such as iron. The figure illustrates the schematic symbol of air and iron core inductors.

INDUCTANCE :

Inductor Behaviour

Inductors or chokes opposes charging currents are said to have inductance and is denote by letter "L"

The behaviour of an inductor can be observed by the following example as shown in the figure.

INDUCTOR BEHAVIOUR :

The rheostat is first adjusted so that the lamps reach the same brightness when the switch is on DC, the resistance R of the rheostat then equals the resistance of the inductors. If the switch is opened and close again, the lamp "L₁" light up a second or two after "L₂" the inductor, which is in series with "L" delays the rise of the DC to its steady value because of its inductance.

If 3 volts battery is replaced by a 3 volts AC supply, the lamp "L" never light because the current is charging all the time. However, it does light if the inductance is reduced by removing the iron core.

To sum up, an 'inductor' allows DC to flow but opposes AC it has the opposite effect to a capacitor. In order to under stand how an inductor works, go through the following lines. "When a conductor is in a charging magnetic field, a voltage is produced in it".

This phenomenon can be done by pushing and withdrawing the magnet, through the inside of the coil, the magnetic field is changed hence a voltage is induced. The ability of this is known as coil – inductance. It can be explained in two ways, i.e. self inductance and mutual inductance.

SELF INDUCTANCE :

It is the ability of a conductor to induce voltage in itself when current changes. It is denote by a letter "L" The self induced voltage V_L across an inductor is shown in the figure

Self Inductance

The self inductance equation is given as

$$V_L = -L \times di/dt$$

- Where
- V_L - Induced voltage in volts
 - L - Inductance in Henries
 - di/dt - rate of change of current in amperes per second

The “minus” sign indicates the polarity of induced voltage which opposes the change in current.

MUTUAL INDUCTANCE :

Mutual Inductance

When two coil are placed closely in such a way that the flux produced in one coil cuts in to the other, then these two coils are said to be magnetically coupled. (Mutually coupled)

As shown in the figure the inductor "L₁" is a flux originated device, with an applied alternating source. Varying current in L₁ induces voltage across "L₁" and L₂ even though "L₂" is not connected to "L₁" because "L₂" is magnetically coupled to "L₁". The property of this arrangement is referred as mutual inductance. It is the ability of a varying current in one inductor to

$$I_m = K\sqrt{L_1L_2}$$

induce voltage in another inductor near by. Its symbol is "L_m" and measured in Henries. It is mathematically expressed as

where K is the co-efficient of coupling between two inductors. The degree of magnetic coupling is known as co-efficient of coupling. It is further defined as, the ratio of flux linkage between L₁ and L₂ to total flux produced by L₁. The value of "K" is always less than a unity.

TYPES OF INDUCTORS :

According to Core Material :

Generally magnetic and non – magnetic material are used as core. Air ceramic, plastic and glass are non – magnetic core materials. These chokes are called as air core chokes or air core inductors. Iron core chokes are the other types in which cobalt, nickel alloys are used as a core.

According to Operating Frequency :

These are two types of chokes, such as AF chokes and RF chokes. The figure shows schematic symbol of chokes.

(a) AF Choke

(b) RF Choke

AF CHOKES :

AF chokes are generally iron – core coils. In its construction it has several hundred of turns on iron core to give high inductance values. Because of high inductance values these chokes suffer from core saturation, in order to avoid this an air gap is maintained in the core. These chokes are either used as filter chokes in radio and TV receivers or as modulation chokes in transmitters. For modulating the carrier air gaps also helps to stabilize the inductance for changes in DC current and reduces the distortion introduced by hysteresis curve. The typical values of A.F. chokes are not more than 5 Henries.

RF CHOKES :

R.F. chokes have smaller inductance value than A.F. chokes. According to the area of application the number of turns varies from one to several hundreds. These are used to select the desired RF signal and reject all others in conjunction with capacitor. These are also used to prevent the flow of RF Currents. RF Chokes use either air as powdered iron slug as core.

DIFFERENT TYPES OF INDUCTORS :

1. Inductor (Air core)

2. Iron core inductor

3. Ferrite core inductor

4. Variable Inductor

5. Trimmer inductor

6. Variable (Ferrite cored) inductor

7. Variable (Iron Cored) inductor

Three main characteristics of dielectric material influence the physical form of capacitor.

1. Dielectric constant
2. Dielectric strength
3. Power factor

CAPACITOR

CAPACITOR :

It is an electronic component which exhibits the property or capacitance.

OR

Electric components, which can store electric charge are called capacitor.

CAPACITANCE :

The property of a Capacitor is known as capacitance.

Symbol :

UNIT OF CAPACITANCE :

The amount of charge Q stored in the capacitor is proportional to the applied voltage. Also a large capacitor can store more charge $Q = CV$ coulombs. Then one coulomb is stored in the dielectric with potential difference of one volt then the capacitance is one farad.

CAPACITOR CHARACTERISTICS :

Three main characteristics of dielectric medium influence the physical form of capacitor.

1. Dielectric constant
2. Dielectric strength
3. Power factor

DIELECTRIC CONSTANT :

It is a numerical quantity expressed as the ratio of the capacitance of a capacitor with a dielectric other than air to the capacitance with air as dielectric. It is represented by " ϵ_r " and also known as relative permittivity.

DIELECTRIC STRENGTH :

The property of the dielectric by which it withstands break down when a voltage applied to it the dielectric strength is expressed in volts per meter of dielectric thickness.

FACTORS AFFECTING THE DIELECTRIC STRENGTH:

- a) Dielectric strength decreases with increase in thickness of dielectric.
- b) It decrease with increase in temperature.
- c) It decreases with increase in humidity.

POWER FACTOR :

The quality of a capacitor in terms of minimum loss is often indicated by its power factor. It gives the fraction of input power dissipated as heat loss in the capacitor.

TYPES OF CAPACITORS :

1. Fixed capacitors
2. Variable capacitors

Fixed capacitors :

- a) Ceramic capacitor
- b) Paper capacitor

- c) Mica capacitor
- d) Electrolytic capacitor
- e) Polyester capacitor
- f) Tantalum electrolytic capacitor

CAPACITOR SPECIFICATIONS :

The main specifications

1. Value of capacitance
2. Tolerance
3. Voltage rating
4. Temperature coefficient
5. Leakage resistance
6. Frequency range
7. Dielectric constant
8. Dielectric strength
9. Power factor
10. Stability

CLASSIFICATIONS :

Mica capacitor, glass capacitor, paper capacitor, ceramic, polyester an electrolyte capacitor.

SYMBOLS OF CAPACITOR :

1. Variable capacitor

2. Polarised Capacitor

3. Trimmer Capacitor

APPLICATIONS :

1. Paper capacitors are used as blocking, coupling and decoupling in low frequency amplifier circuits.
2. Mica capacitors are used in radio frequency circuit for the same purpose less and polystyrene capacitors are also used in high frequency Ckt. Electrolytic capacitors are used in pure supply circuit suppressing of AC ripples.
3. These are used for blocking buffer by pass and filters capacitors an in power applications for power factor correction and motor latching.
4. Mica capacitors are used for high voltage, high current radio frequency circuit in transmitters. They are used in high frequency filters as coupling capacitors and for turning at high frequencies.

EQUALIZERS (CERAMIC FILTER)

INTRODUCTION :

Electronic circuit exhibit non uniform attenuation and phase delay with variation in frequency. It is not desirable in circuits as it amounts to distortion of signals in a working frequency range under ideal conditions the attenuation and phase delay must be the same in the entire frequency range. Equalizers are circuits designed and used to obtain overall uniform response of the total working frequency range.

TYPES OF EQUALIZERS :

Based on type of equalization, two types of equalizers are present.

- a) Attenuation or Amplitude equalizers and
- b) Phase or delay equalizer

Based on type of configuration two types are there

1. series type equalizers and
2. shunt type equalizers

DISTINCTION BETWEEN SERIES AND SHUNT EQUALIZERS :

The series equalizer is connected in series with the sending or receiving end of the network to be corrected. It is in series with the load also.

The shunt equalizer is connected in shunt with the sending or receiving end of the network to be equalized.

NEED FOR FOUR TERMINAL EQUALIZER :

Two terminal equalizers either the shunt type or the series type, suffers from the draw back that its impedance varies with frequency causing impedance mismatch and consequent reflection losses. To avoid these difficulties a four terminal is preferred because it offers a constant impedance and hence avoids reflection losses when terminated in its design impedance.

CONSTANT RESISTANCE EQUALIZER :

It is a four terminal equalizer using series and shunt arm impedance, which are inverse of each other with respect to a constant resistance usually, the design resistance of the equalizer. Such an equalizer always presents a constant input and output resistance at all frequencies.

SIMPLE FOUR TERMINAL CONSTANT RESISTANCE EQUALIZER :

TDA 2822

TDA 2822 CIRCUITS :

The TDA 2822 is a versatile dual amplifier that can use any DC supply in the range between 1.8V to 15V, it can be powered from a 3V supply and used to drive headphones ones at 20 mw per 32 ohm channel or from a 9V supply and used to drive 8 ohm speaker at 1w per channel.

The TDA 2822 is housed in an 8 pin dual package and uses the minimum of external components.

Outline and pin notations of the TDA 2822 dual amplifier IC.

The above circuit is TDA 2822 stereo amplifier. It can be used as a stereo speaker or head phone amplifier powered from a 6v supply.

PRINTED CIRCUIT BOARD

PCB's are certainly the most important element in the fabrication of electronic equipment. It is the design of properly laid out PCB's that determines many of the limiting properties with respect to noise immunity as well as to fast pulse, high frequency and low level of the equipment. The fabrication process also will determine to a large extent the price and reliability of the equipment.

LAYOUT :

The layout of a PCB has to incorporate all the information on the board before one can go on to the art work preparation. This means that a concept that clearly defines all the details of the circuit and partly also have the final equipment is a prerequisite before the actual layout can start.

Depending on the accuracy required, artwork should be produced at a 1:1 or 1:2 or even 1:4 scale. Normally 1:4 scale applied have very high precision required and 1:1 scale is preferred for single sided board. The artwork is usually preferred on transparent base foil with a black taping is widely accepted as an industry standard. For small boards drawing and slip artwork are satisfactory. The design of out work has become simple and more efficient. The taps are available in standard widths of 0.5 mm, 1 mm, 2 mm and 8mm widths.

After completing the procedure, the above is written. It is not obsolete. The present trends of artwork is done with computer software like electronic workbench, circuit makes and CAD.

CALSSIFICATION OF PCB :

Single Sided Boards :

The single sided PCB are mostly used in entertainment electronics at the minimum manufacturing cost. Also they are used in industrial electronics. Normally the thickness of the laminate will be 1.6 mm with good mechanical properties.

Double sided boards :

Double sided PCB can be made with or without plated through holes. They are used when there is circuit complexity and density. The no of plated through holes should be minimized for reasons of economy and reliability. A laminate of thickness 3.2 mm is used for special purpose applications.

Multi Layer Boards :

A part from double sided PCB, multi layer PCB, (8 layers, 16 layers) are also put to use in ordinary complex circuit applications. On PCB laminates of copper foils of 35 mm thickness are preferable employed. Even 70 mm and 105 mm thickness foils also can be used. To reduce skin effect losses PCB, thickness should be increased. To reduce the radiation losses thickness should be decreased.

PREPERATION OF PCB :

The artwork is usually prepared on transparent base foil with a black taping is widely accepted as an industry standard. For small boards ink drawings and skip artwork are satisfactory. The availability of self adhesive taper are available in standard widths of 0.5 mm, 1 mm, 2 mm, 4mm and 8mm widths. After completion of the artwork on the base foil the out lines of the PCB are identified by suitable corner marking with 1mm tape. These

tapers are fixed outside the actual PCB area. After fixing the boundaries of the PCB the next step is to fix all the pads. The pads are placed exactly and properly where desired the taping of conductors is now completed giving the actual circuit desired.

CLEANING OF COPPER CLAD BOARD :

The basic raw material required for PCB is copper clad laminate. The fine copper layer on the laminate is cladding. The laminate material is classified into two types as glass epoxy (FG) and synthetic resin bonded paper (phenolic).

The FG type is generally used for high frequency and high temperature environments as it has low dielectric loss with temperature stability.

The copper clad laminate is to be thoroughly cleaned for organic substance like oil and grease by a suitable solvent. After this, the cleaned laminate is dipped in hydrochloric acid to remove the alkali and metallic oxides.

PRINTING :

After the preparation of the copper laminate and the artwork, the artwork is to be printed on the copper clad laminate. The methods used are in different ways, the simplest way is to hand print the circuit pattern on the copper clad laminate by acid resistant ink like markers, enamel paints even nail polish can be used.

The other two methods employed are photo printing and screen printing. Photo printing is extremely precise and costly and hence used in professional applications. Screen printing is comparatively cheap even

though with less precision. Thus it is widely used for most of the applications when the ultimate accuracy and precision is not necessary.

ETCHING :

Etching is a process, where the final copper pattern is formed and the unwanted copper is removed. After the unwanted copper is removed, the process should be stopped otherwise it leads to reduction in the conductor size and width. Generally spray etching and bubble etching are the two methods employed for this purpose. The etchants in use are ferric chloride, cupric chloride, chromic acid and alkaline ammonia.

CLEANING :

The laminate is thoroughly washed in water after etching is completed the paint is then removed with alcohol or acetone.

DRILLING & TINNING :

The next major operation after etching is the drilling of holes. The diameter of the holes varies from component to components. It is 1 mm for ICs, 1.25 mm for resistor and capacitors and 1.5 mm for diodes. The oxidation of the copper portion can be prevented by either tinning that can be done by using a soldering iron or by giving it a coat of some insulating varnish.

SOLDERING OF COMPONENTS :

Place the components on a PCB properly according to a component layout and solder the components taking proper care.

TESTING :

Check the continuity of the conductor track and prepare soldering with help of multimeter.

PRECAUTIONS :

1. Outmost care should be taken while copying the circuit on to the copper clad.
2. While etching the PCB it should not go on either under etched or over etched.
3. While drawing the PCB layout the original track thickness should be thin. The power supply track should be medium thick and the ground track should be very thick.
4. The no. of tracks and pads should be minimized.
5. Discontinuities should not be there between pad and conducting paths.
6. Usage of jumpers should be minimized
7. Avoid short circuit
8. After the unwanted copper is removed the etching process should be stopped.
9. Avoid dry soldering
10. Avoid loose connection.

RESULTS

This project is completed successfully. On placing the metal near the sensor (Inductor) sound is produced and sound is stopped when metal is removed.

COMPONENTS LIST

<i>Name of the Component</i>	<i>Value of Component</i>	<i>Quantity</i>
Resistors	330 Ω	(1)
	330 k Ω	(5)
	1 k Ω	(5)
	10 k Ω	(5)
Variable Resistor log	10 k Ω	(1)
	4.7 Ω	(2)
Capacitors	Trimmer 0 – 22 pF	(1)
	100 μ f 25V	(2)
	1 μ f 16V	(1)
	10 nf	(7)
	15 nF	(2)
	0.1 μ F	(2)
	100 nF	(2)
	100 pF	(1)
	470 pF	(1)
Transistors	BF 494	(3)

Diodes	0A79	(2)
Ceramic filter	5.5 MHz	(1)
IC	TDA 2822	(1)
Loud speaker	8 ohm, 1w	(1)
Inductor 20 turns of (25 SWG) 4" Dia air core		(1)
Printed Circuit Board	1/2 foot square.	(1)

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